

Journal of Social and Political Sciences

Prasrirataesang, Narintip, and Ayuwat, Dusadee. (2019), Factors Associated to Work-life Balance of Industrial and Service Labours, Thailand. In: *Journal of Social and Political Sciences*, Vol.2, No.3, 497-503.

ISSN 2615-3718

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1991.02.03.90

The online version of this article can be found at:
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Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

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Factors Associated to Work-life Balance of Industrial and Service Labours, Thailand

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Abstract

This research aims to study factors that associated to work-life balance on dimension work/personal life enhancement of industrial and service labours. The quantitative methodology was employed with individual level as a unit of analysis. The sample consisted of 397 labours who are working in industrial and service sectors that random by systematic random sampling. The data were collected using the interview schedule from May to June 2018 and analyzed by descriptive statistics and Chi-square. The results showed that most of the labours (75.3 percentages) were female. Age of labours samples in the generation Y (19-38 years old) 63.5 percentages. The labours samples have got married (43.2 percentages). More than haft of them finished secondary school. There are 74.1 percentages of labours samples worked in industrial and service sectors less than 10 years and more than haft worked per day more than 8 hours that over than the regulation by labour law. When analyzing factors associated to work-life balance on dimension work/personal life enhancement of industrial and service labours with Chi-square, it was found that the personnel characteristics factors (education level) and work condition factors (working hours per day) were the factors that associated to work-life balance on dimension work/personal life enhancement of female labours while in the male labour the personnel characteristics factors (age , marital status, education level) and work condition factors (working session in organization and working hours per day) were the factors that associated to work-life balance on dimension work/personal life enhancement of male labours.

Keywords: Work-life Balance, Personal Life Enhancement, Industrial and Service Labours

Introduction

The working age population has been an effective group to the economic of the country. Their workforces are the fundamental of the industrial sector and service sector, as a tool driving the growth of the economic system (Amadeo, 2018). However, the complexity of working condition in the industrial sector and service sector has caused unpleasant conditions to labours. Labours have to work hardly under rules and regulations of workplaces. For instance, some works with heavy machines, taking care of the customers, using a new form of technology, and different working conditions. Those working conditions have caused workers unable to manage their personal life

and work appropriately. Therefore, it is important to focus on the labour group in the industrial sector and the service sector. To have a good working life, labours should adjust personal life and work appropriately. This circumstance called the work-life balance. Labours should have a balance between personal life and work, especially on the personal life and work enhancement, which causes positive outcomes to labours themselves (Fisher, 2003). Encouraging a balance between personal life and work to labours will result in an appropriate time management of labours. Labours would reduce work stress, and have a positive interrelationship with family. These outcomes are directly linked to production efficiency and services, and it is a management of human resources in an organization (Guest, 2002)

Females, currently, has been entering increasingly into works in the economic part. Females once were set their roles and functions only at home, both male labours and female labours, however, have shifted their works from works in the agricultural sector into labours in the industrial sector and service sector (Worawan, 2018). Therefore, it is interesting to investigate how do male labours, and female labours in the industrial sector and service sector have a work-life balance on work and personal life enhancement? and what factors associated to work-life balance on work and personal life enhancement? The implication of research is provided to launch the policy recommendations on working life of labours.

Research Objective

To examine factors associated to work-life balance on work and personal life enhancement among labours in the industrial sector and service sector.

Concepts and Literature reviews

This paper reviews a concept of **Work-Life Balance (WLB)** as per the following details:

Work and life balance refers to the management of personal life (self, family, and society) and work appropriately. In the capitalism society, Marx (1884) describes the management of personal life and time. Marx suggested that time management is an attempt to control any actions in the system. Time of individuals in the capitalism is divided into 2 types: 1) work Time is the time that labours sell their own labour forces in order to receive wages in the industrial system, and 2) life time is the time spent by labours to rest or relax before returning to work. Therefore, labours must have a balance between personal life and work.

Fisher (2003) identified dimensions of the work-life balance in 3 dimensions including 1) work interference with personal life (WIPL) which resulted in difficulty of life adjustment, 2) personal life interference with work (PLIW) which resulted in difficulty of working adjustment, and 3) work and personal life enhancement (WPLE) which resulted in positive effects to both personal life and working.

It is concluded that labours should make a balance between personal life and work on work and personal life enhancement in order to achieve their work and life balances. This paper, therefore, is interested in work and personal life enhancement dimension by defining that; labours in the industry sector and service sector who have appropriate work-life balance, they shall be enhancing their personal life and work in order to achieve their work and life goals

Several studies have conducted investigations on factors correlated to work-life balance. Wendy (2010) examined the relationship between social support, work and family balance, and working performance of the middle-aged women in the United States. The results found there were correlations between incomes and social support, and the correlation between incomes and work and family balance. In general, women received social support on the person rather than social support on work. It also found that social support on work positively correlated with job satisfaction, occupational stability, and occupational achievement. Dolai (2015) studied the work-life balance of insurance business employees in India. The results found that there was no significant difference in work-life

balance among the respondents. Females had personal life interference with work more than males, while males had work interference with personal life rather than females. The results indicated that there was a correlation between sex and work-life balance. Mustafa (2015) studies the work-life balance of female sewing labours in Bangladesh. The results found that factors contributed work-life balance to female employees consisted of high incomes, reduced workload, and flexible working hours.

Richert (2016) examined work-life balance and the increasing age of labours in Finland. It is found that the higher age contributed better work-life balance to labours. Older labours would have more satisfaction in work-life balance than younger labours, and labours who aged between 55-70 years old had work-life balance the most. Hakobyan (2017) studied factors influenced on achievement in work-life balance among women in the United States. The influenced factors consisted of sufficient rest time, appropriate working schedule, and family support.

In conclusion, factors correlate work-life balance consists of 1) characteristics factor including age, marital status, and education 2) working condition factor including job position, monthly income, number of the year worked at the workplace, and working hours per day. Therefore, this paper raises the research hypothesis that work-life balance on work and personal life enhancement among labours in the industrial sector and service sector has correlated with characteristics factor and working condition factor.

Research methodology

Quantitative methodology with the cross-sectional design was employed in the study. Unit of analysis was at the individual level. The population was 53,996 legal Thai labours who aged over 18 years old working for enterprises in the industrial and services sector in Khon Kaen province. The sample size was 397 cases calculated by Yamane's formula, and sampling was done by Multi-stage sampling method. The research instrument was interview schedule which developed from concepts and related literature. Interview schedule consisted of 3 parts included characteristics of respondents, working conditions, and work-life balance on work and personal life enhancement. Interview schedule was reviewed by external experts to clarify content validity and tried out with reliability of 0.864.

Questions of work-life balance on work and personal life enhancement consisted of 8 rating-scale items with 4 choices always included (4 points), often (3 points), sometimes (2 points), never (1 point). Dependent variable was work-life balance in work and personal life enhancement. Interval scale was applied to the study and adjusted into 2 referential groups included (1) work-life imbalance (8.0-20.0 points), and (2) work-life balance (21.0-32.0 points).

Data collection conducted during May to June 2018. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze characteristics of respondents, while analysis on factors correlated work-life balance on work and personal life enhancement was done by Chi-square statistic. Contingency Coefficient (CC.) was applied to identify correlated level which divided into 3 levels included 1) fairly low (CC. = 0.001-0.500), 2) medium (CC. = 0.501-0.700), and 3) fairly high (CC. = 0.701-1.000) (Field, 2002). Results were presented by descriptions with tables.

Results

Research results consist of 3 parts including 1) characteristics of labours and working conditions, 2) work-life balance on work and personal life enhancement, and 3) factors correlate work-life balance on work and personal life enhancement, as follows.

1) Characteristics of labours and working conditions

The results indicated that a majority of labour (63.5 percent) were in the Generation Y, and the average age of them was 35.4 years old (43.1 percent). Most of the labours maintained marriage status and lived with a spouse,

and 38.0 percent of labours maintain single marital status. 55.2 percent maintained education level below junior high school. In addition, it was found that three fourth of labours were female. This indicated that female has been entering increasingly into works in the economic system.

Regarding working conditions, 22.4 percent of labours held the supervisor position, and 77.6 percent held operative labour position. Most of them had a working period less than 10 years (Mean = 8.1, S.D. = 8.1), and 76.5 percent of them earned a monthly income less than \$478.15 because most of them maintained education level lower than the Bachelor degree. The study also found that female labours worked hardly. More than a half of female labours had working hours over 8 hours per day, and 9.6 percent of them worked more than 12 hours per day, in which it was noncompliance with the national labour law (Ministry of Labour, 2017)

2) Work-life balance on work and personal life enhancement

Results on work-life balance on work and personal life enhancement revealed 73.3 percent of labours had work-life balance, while more than one-fourth of them had work-life imbalance due to the role of labour in the industrial sector and the service sector in which the working conditions were less flexible. Labours had to comply with rules and regulations set by enterprises. In addition, more than a half of labour worked over 8 hours per day, which was noncompliance to the national labour law, so some labours could not adjust their personal life and work appropriately.

3) Factors associated to work-life balance on work and personal life enhancement

This analytical part on factors correlated work-life balance on work and personal life enhancement input characteristic factor, working condition factor, and work-life balance on work and personal life enhancement factor in the study. The results were presented as follows.

Characteristic factor

Age; male labour (81.1 percent) who were in the Generation Y (19-38 years old) had work-life balance, while more than a half of labour which was in the Baby Boomer Generation (over 54 years old) had a work-life imbalance. Correlation analysis found that there was a correlation of 0.265 between the age of male labours and work-life balance on work and personal life enhancement with a statistical significance level of 0.05. It was different from female labours aged in the Baby Boomer Generation (82.6 percent) who had work-life balance.

The study also found that female labours aged in the Generation Y (19-38 years old) (30.0 percent) had a work-life imbalance, and correlation analysis did not found a correlation between age of female labours and work-life balance on work and personal life enhancement with a statistical significance level of 0.05. Therefore, it is concluded that a correlation between age of labours and work-life balance is found among male labour group only. The result confirmed Angrisani (2017) who explored that the different ages of males resulted in a better work-life balance than females.

Marital status; male labours (88.3 percent) and female labours (78.8 percent) with single status had work-life balance in which its ratio was higher than labours with a spouse because labours with single status did not have to take care of familial works. Moreover, it was clear that male labours with a spouse had a ratio of work-life imbalance higher than female labours because male labours had advancement in their works. Some had been promoted to higher positions which higher responsible for job assignments. Regarding correlation analysis, it was found that there was a correlation of 0.233 between marriage status of male labours and work-life balance on work and personal life enhancement with a statistical significance level of 0.05, while there was no correlation between marriage status of female labours and work-life balance on work and personal life enhancement with a statistical significance level of 0.05. Regarding **education**, found that male labours (94.7 percent) and female labours (88.0 percent) who maintain Bachelor degree had work-life balance, and male labours (31.8 percent) who maintain

educational degree lower than Bachelor degree had a work-life imbalance, in which its ratio was higher than female labours. There were correlations of 0.245 and 0.186 between education and work-life balance of male labours and female labours, respectively, with a statistical significance level of 0.05. The result confirmed Flora's study (2010) revealing that education had influenced the role and work-life balance among hotel employee (table 1)

Table 1: The percentage of labours classified according to characteristics factors and work-life balance on personal life enhancement

Characteristics	Work-life Balance on Dimension Work/ Personal Life Enhancement					
	Male labours			Female labours		
	Work-life Balance	Work-life Imbalance	Total	Work-life Balance	Work-life Imbalance	Total
1. Age						
Generation Z (≥ 18 years old)	0.0	0.0	100.0 (0)	100.0	0.0	100.0 (2)
Generation Y (19-38 years old)	81.8	18.2	100.0 (55)	70.7	29.3	100.0 (188)
Generation X (39-53 years old)	66.7	33.3	100.0 (21)	76.7	23.3	100.0 (86)
Baby boomer (≤ 54 years old)	44.4	55.6	100.0 (9)	82.6	17.4	100.0 (23)
	Pearson Chi-square = 6.439 df = 2 Significance = 0.040 CC. = 0.265			Pearson Chi-square = 2.903 df = 3 Significance = 0.407		
2. marital status						
Single	88.3	16.7	100.0 (48)	78.8	21.2	100.0 (118)
With spouse	62.2	37.8	100.0 (37)	70.2	29.8	100.0 (181)
	Pearson Chi-square = 4.882 df = 1 Significance = 0.027 CC. = 0.233			Pearson Chi-square = 2.748 df = 1 Significance = 0.097		
3. education						
Lower than Bachelor degree	68.2	31.8	100.0 (66)	68.8	31.2	100.0 (224)
Bachelor degree	94.7	5.3	100.0 (19)	88.0	12.0	100.0 (75)
	Pearson Chi-square = 5.423 df = 1 Significance = 0.020 CC. = 0.245			Pearson Chi-square = 10.710 df = 1 Significance = 0.001 CC. = 0.186		

Working condition factor

Job position; 77.8 percent of male labours had work-life balance in which its ratio was higher than female labours who held the same position. Male labours who maintained a supervisor position (36.4 percent) had a work-life imbalance in which its ratio was higher than female labours who maintain supervisor position. In addition, there were no correlations between job position of male labours and female labours and work-life balance with a statistical significance level of 0.05. Regarding **monthly income**, found that male labours (60.9 percent) and female labours (82.1 percent) who received monthly income more than \$471.25 had work-life balance, while female labours (30.0 percent) who received monthly income less than \$471.25 had a work-life imbalance. In addition, there were no correlations between monthly incomes of male labours and female labours and work-life balance with a statistical significance level of 0.05

The number of the year worked at the workplace; found that more than half of male labours who had worked for their workplaces more than 16 years had a work-life imbalance. Male labours and female labours who were in other age had a ratio of work-life balance higher than groups with work-life imbalance. In addition, there was a correlation of 0.329 between a number of the years worked at the workplace of male labours and work-life balance with a statistical significance level of 0.05. These findings were different from correlation analysis among female labours which found that there was no correlation between the number of the years worked at the workplace of female labours and work-life balance with a statistical significance level of 0.05

Working hours; found that group of male labours and group of female labours had the same pattern of work-life balance. One-third of both male labours and female labours worked more than 8 hours had a ratio of work-life imbalance. In addition, there were correlations of 0.210 and 0.172 between working hours and work-life balance of male labours and female labours respectively, with a statistical significance level of 0.05. The result confirmed

Hakobyan's study (2017) revealing that appropriate working schedule, and appropriate working hours were factors contributed work-life balance among female (table 2)

Table 2: The percentage of labours classified according to working condition factor and work-life balance on personal life enhancement

Working condition	Work-life Balance on Dimention Work/ Personal Life Enhancement					
	Male labours			Female labours		
	Work-life Balance	Work-life Imbalance	Total	Work-life Balance	Work-life Imbalance	Total
1. job position						
Supervisor position	63.6	36.4	100.0 (22)	79.4	20.6	100.0 (63)
Operative position	77.8	22.2	100.0 (63)	71.9	28.1	100.0 (236)
	Pearson Chi-square = 1.700 df = 1 Significance = 0.192			Pearson Chi-square = 1.779 df = 2 Significance = 0.441		
2. monthly income						
≥ \$471.25	79.0	21.0	100.0 (62)	71.1	28.9	100.0 (232)
≤ \$471.25	60.9	39.1	100.0 (23)	82.1	17.9	100.0 (67)
	Pearson Chi-square = 2.885 df = 1 Significance = 0.089			Pearson Chi-square = 3.217 df = 1 Significance = 0.073		
3. number of year worked at workplace						
1-5 years	79.2	20.8	100.0 (48)	72.8	27.2	100.0 (151)
6-10 years	91.7	8.3	100.0 (12)	76.4	23.6	100.0 (72)
11-15 years	77.8	22.2	100.0 (9)	66.7	33.3	100.0 (30)
≤ 16 years	43.8	56.2	100.0 (16)	76.1	23.9	100.0 (46)
	Pearson Chi-square = 10.319 df = 3 Significance = 0.016 CC. = 0.329			Pearson Chi-square = 1.220 df = 3 Significance = 0.748		
4. working hours per day						
No more than 8 hr. / day	80.7	19.3	100.0 (57)	82.0	18.0	100.0 (138)
More than 8 hr. / day	60.7	39.3	100.0 (28)	66.5	33.5	100.0 (161)
	Pearson Chi-square = 3.910 df = 1 Significance = 0.048 CC. = 0.210			Pearson Chi-square = 9.094 df = 1 Significance = 0.003 CC. = 0.172		

Conclusion and recommendations

Conclusion; according to the results above, it is concluded that majority of labours in the industrial sector and service sector in Khon Kaen province have work-life balance since locations of the workplace are close to labour's residents. They also have families to support various labour's matters. However, the work-life imbalance is still found among one-fourth of labours especially male labours who held supervisor position, male labours who aged in the Baby Boomer Generation, both male and female labours with spouses, and labours who work more than 8 hours. Therefore, workplaces and related agencies should provide training to labours in order to educate guideline on time management to encourage work-life balance among labours and create mechanism tools for workers to deal with work-life balance smoothly.

Factors correlate work-life balance on work and personal life enhancement among both male labours and female labours consist of education and working hours per day. While factors correlate work-life balance on work and personal life enhancement among male workers consist of age, marital status, education, number of years worked at workplace, and working hours per day, and factors correlate work-life balance on work and personal life enhancement among female labours consist of education, and working hours per day, respectively.

Recommendations; considering factors correlate work-life balance on work and personal life enhancement among female labours, found that guideline on work-life balance should be provided to female labours especially female labours who had educational degree lower than Bachelor degree because education is an effective tool that contributes working opportunities to female labours, and female labours would have opportunity to apply knowledge and skills educated to manage personal life and work appropriately. Moreover, another female labour

groups that should be supported is female labours who work more than 8 hours per day. This female labour group has the main role in the family business, and they also perform as labours in the industrial sector and service sector at the same time. It results in they could not maintain a balance between personal life and work. Therefore, workplaces and related government agencies should schedule a suitable working hour of female labours, and create awareness to female labours not to focus on hard working in order to get economic profits in return until it causes negative effects to their families and themselves. When female labours have appropriate working hours, they will have more time to do an activity with families and friends. This is a way to promote female labours to maintain work-life balance appropriately.

Acknowledgments

The researchers would like to thank the enterprises in the industrial and services sector in Khon Kaen for supporting the avail of this research and gave this research support. My grateful go through Research and Training Center for Enhancing Quality of Life of Working Age People, Khon Kaen University, for their funding support. Finally, the researcher would like to thank the labours in the enterprises in the industrial and services sector for the participation and for giving the researches very useful information.

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